

A study of influence of air-coupled ultrasonic directivity and optimum probe size on nondestructive evaluation

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SUMMARY

Air-coupled ultrasonic inspection has lower resolution than conventional ultrasonic inspections. To enhance a resolution of this method, the influence of air-coupled ultrasonic directivity was evaluated with experiment and analysis. From the result, optimum ultrasonic probe radius which acquires the highest resolution was determined.

Keywords: Air-coupled Ultrasonic, Non-destructive Evaluation, Finite Element Method

INTRODUCTION

Although air-coupled ultrasonic inspection has an advantage not to require any wet couplant, to enhance a resolution of this method is desired because of relatively lower resolution in comparison with conventional ultrasonic inspection [1]. In order to overcome this difficulty, influences of ultrasonic directivity on the air-coupled ultrasonic inspection are evaluated.

ULTRASONIC DIRECTIVITY

For rectangular probes, ultrasonic directivity angle β is approximately obtained by following equation [2],

$$\beta = 57 \cdot \frac{\lambda}{b} \quad (1)$$

where λ is wavelength and b is side length of probes.

EXPERIMENT AND DISCUSSION

Experiments were carried out by transmission C-scan mode. The distance between transducer and receiver was set to 30mm, and CFRP specimen (5mm thick with a delamination) was set in the center of two probes. Transmitted wave from the transducer consisted of a frequency sweep from 280 kHz to 480 kHz over a time period of 200 μ s. Acquired C-scan image is shown in Fig.1. In the image, fuzzy area exists near the edge of the specimen. Its length is 15.8mm. The existence of this area contributes to poor resolution. By using Eq. (1), ultrasonic beam width at the specimen position can be calculated to be 15.2mm. This value almost corresponds to the length of fuzzy area.

Fig. 1 Ultrasonic C-scan image of CFRP specimen with delamination

DETERMINATION OF OPTIMUM PROBE SIZE

From the previous discussion, the length of fuzzy area depends on the length of beam width. Consequently, the narrowest beam width makes the highest resolution. Fig. 2 shows relation between beam width and probe radius of circular probes. It shows a probe with a radius of 2.3 mm forms minimum beam width. From this result, probes with radius 2.3 mm are the optimum size for the highest resolution. This was confirmed by FEM (Finite Element Method) analysis using a model of the same situation as the experiment.

Fig. 2 Relation between probe radius and ultrasonic beam width

References

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